

A STUDY OF AWARENESS OF CLIMATE EDUCATION AMONGST STUDENTS OF STD IX IN ANDHERI

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"The world will not be destroyed by those who do evil, but by those who watch them without doing anything." -- Albert Einstein

Life affects the composition of the atmosphere and therefore the climate because different life forms take in and release gases like carbon dioxide, methane and oxygen at different rates. Climatic conditions help to shape various ecosystems and habitats around the globe. A particular climate can be a boon to one species and devastation to another.

As the climate changes, species and ecosystems respond by adapting, migrating, or reducing their population. Gradual shifts in the climate are easier to adapt to than abrupt swings, and this is certainly true for humans as well as other species. Studies of Earth's climatic history indicate that climates have changed in the past and resulted in dramatic shifts in ecosystems.

Human beings have been influencing climate in many ways in terms of land use changes, irrigation of farmland, draining of wetlands, and the modification of the earth – atmospheric energy balance, through the release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Other sources of anthropogenic emission leading to the warming of the atmosphere, usually referred to as the greenhouse effect, include: inputs from fossil fuel consumption, cement manufacture, flaring of natural gas, bush burning and agricultural practices. The human activities dominating the modern day climate are now large enough to exceed the bounds of the natural variability and many environmental studies has affirmed that the dominant causes of climate change are human activities. Climate change is the shift in the mean state of the climate over an extended period of time (decades or longer) which may be due to natural changes or prolonged

anthropogenic changes in the state of the atmosphere or in land use. The natural activities including ocean currents, solar variations and El Nino could be short or long term events. El Nino which is an example of natural climatic variability releases heat from the ocean which eventually causes a general positive anomalies in global mean temperature by shifting heat around different parts of climate system. It also causes changes in precipitation pattern, floods and drought intensity across the world. El Nino occurrence is irregular, but it has an average periodicity of 4 years. Its impacts are felt most and strongest in the tropics.

Need of the study

Education gives us knowledge of the world around us and changes it into something better. It develops in us a perspective of looking at life. It helps us build opinions and have points of view on things in life. People debate over the subject of whether **education** is the only thing that gives knowledge. This study will helps learners to understand the causes and consequences of **climate change**, prepares them to live with the impacts of **climate change** and empowers learners to take appropriate actions to adopt more sustainable lifestyles

AIM OF THE STUDY

The following was the broad aim of the study:

1. To study the awareness of climate education of secondary school students.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the awareness of climate education of secondary school students
2. To compare the following variable among secondary school students on the basis of their gender:

- i) Awareness of climate education

Hypothesis: (Null Hypothesis):

The following null hypotheses have been formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant gender difference in the following variable among secondary school students:

- i) Awareness of climate education

2. There is no significant relationship between awareness of climate education among secondary school students
- i) Boy students.
 - ii) Girl students.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study, an attempt has been made to investigate awareness of climate education girls and boys of Secondary school students in Mumbai. In order to achieve the pre-determined objectives of the study, the researcher has planned the entire process of the work in terms of research design.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

Descriptive Survey research design is adopted in the investigation of the students' awareness on the issues of climate change education. The use of questionnaire was adopted in the gathering of data. The instrument for Data collection for this study is mainly a well-structured and developed questionnaire. The collection was done personally by the researchers and the data analysis approach used in this study includes both the descriptive and inferential statistical analyses which entail frequency counts and percentage

SAMPLE

For the purpose of the study, 444 secondary school students (girls and boys) studying in std. IX. From five secondary schools in Andheri and Vile Parle.

TESTS USED AND THEIR DESCRIPTION

The researcher used the Rosenberg's self esteem in that questionnaire item no. 1,2,4,6,7,8 were positive question and item no.3,5,8,9,10 were negative questions.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION

After collecting the test scales along with the scoring keys, the investigator contacted the Secondary School students. A brief description of test scales along with the objectives and importance of the study were explained to the subjects to ensure their honest, correct and sincere responses. They were asked to give responses as per the first reply that comes

to their mind after reading each question carefully.

STATISTICAL PROCEDURE

Mean score and standard deviation of Boys students (N=171), Girls students (N=273), and schools (N=5) and the sample (N=442) were calculated in one variable i.e. awareness of climate education. One-way analysis of variance was applied to find out the significance of mean difference among students of the variable. This was followed by Significance Difference Test (L.S.D.) to determine the significance of difference between ordered paired means at 0.05 & 0.01 levels.

INFERENTIAL ANALYSIS.

Testing Hypothesis 1

The null hypothesis states that there is no significant gender difference in the following variables among secondary school students:

- Awareness of climate education

The technique used to test this hypothesis is the 't' test, Variables: awareness of climate education

Groups	N	d-f	Mean	Standard Division	t-ratio	Table Value		Significance level
						0.05	0.01	
Boys	171	442	86.54	6.49	1.39	1.93	2.59	NS
Girls	273		85.77	7.42				

Interpretation

From the table it can be seen that the obtained t- ratio of 1.39 does not exceed the 't' critical value of 1.96 necessary for rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant . Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in Awareness of climate education scores of students on the basis of gender. Thus from the findings it can be said that boys and girls students are having similar awareness of climate education.

Result:

There is no significant difference between boys and girls Awareness of climate education

Testing Hypothesis 2

The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the following Variable among secondary school teachers on the basis of type of management.

The technique used to test this hypothesis is the 't' test, Variables: Job Stress

Groups	N	d-f	Mean	Standard Division	t-ratio	Table Value		Significance level
						0.05	0.01	
Aided	211	442	85.47	7.42	0.29	1.96	2.59	NS
Unaided	233		86.27	8.69				

Interpretation

From the table it can be seen that the obtained t- ratio are less than the table value. Thus 't' is not significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in awareness of climate education on the basis of type of management. Thus from the findings it can be said that secondary school students from different type of management i.e. aided and unaided secondary school students are having similar awareness about climate change.

Result

There is no significant difference between aided and unaided school students in awareness of climate education

Finding & Conclusion:

- There is no significant difference between boys and girls Awareness of climate education.
- There is no significant difference between aided and unaided school students in awareness of climate education.

Suggestions:

- School should provide various exposures through various activities.e.g Quiz, expert talks, films.
- Instead of teaching climate change as a subject on its own, several educators are pushing for the topic to be embedded in different subjects.

- “At the end of the unit, as a culminating project, students chose groups, researched current solutions for physical and economic water scarcity and created PSA videos using iMovie about the problem and how their solution could help to combat the issue.”

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